

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES: NEW OPPORTUNITIES IN TELEVISION

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Abstract. *This article presents the possibilities of television in today's information age, proposals for its development, and television, as the most widely watched media, cannot lag behind other types of media, and TV does not lose its relevance when it adapts to the times.*

Keywords: *television, technology, political, media, personnel.*

In the context of the rapid development of digital technologies and their significant impact on political communications, the study of modern technologies used to create the image of politicians on television is of particular importance. New video production and image processing tools provide unprecedented opportunities, but at the same time increase the risk of manipulating public opinion. Analysis of the balance between authenticity and artificiality in creating a politician's television image is the key to understanding modern political reality and is necessary for the formation of critical thinking among citizens. Therefore, the study of technological approaches to the formation of the image of politicians on television is necessary to ensure awareness and prevent manipulation.

In modern democratic states, political parties are a socio-political institution, and the issue of the perception of their image by citizens is of particular interest. Radical changes in the public consciousness, changes in the perception of images, their semantic content are caused by political changes taking place in modern society. Political parties are experiencing serious changes both at the institutional level and at the level of formation and perception of their image by the public consciousness. Today, political parties are forced to quickly adapt to new conditions, which always entails radical changes in both the party structure and party policy.

Mediatization is pushing political parties to inevitably use mechanisms to attract voters through the media.

The dynamism of the modern information and media environment continues to create significant, sometimes unexpected changes that have a significant impact on democratic governance. This has changed the conduct of elections, the participation of citizens in political life. Due to the development of the media, the working methods of state institutions have fundamentally changed, their activities have become more transparent, changes have occurred in the organization of elections, which also affected the involvement of citizens in this process.

In this context, this paragraph is about modern technologies used to create the image of politicians on television, and the analysis will focus on technological aspects and their impact on audience perception.

Modern editing technologies create wide opportunities for shaping the image of a politician on television. The dynamics of editing, the selection of frames and the use of special effects can significantly affect the audience's perception of the image of a politician. Fast editing can create the impression of energy and dynamism, while slow editing can create the impression of calm and confidence. Smart shots allow you to show the desired qualities of a politician.

These include using close-ups to show emotion or using wide shots to emphasize its impact and importance. Special effects, although rarely used in political advertising, can create a certain mood or emphasize the importance of the event.¹

As in any game, there are certain rules in editing:

The first rule states that it is necessary to produce a specific video product in all respects, taking into account the lighting, color scheme and sound, along with visual images. The combination of these factors creates what is called the editing style. Deviations from the chosen style are allowed, but again as a conscious “game”, this is done by the director or TV journalist to achieve a certain expressive task.

The second rule is that the editing procedure should be thought out in advance and precede the filming process: an "editing sheet" is drawn up in advance, that is, a schedule where everything that happens in the video is recorded. This stage of work helps to determine which frames will be combined in the subsequent editing and how to place cameras and lighting.

Lighting also plays an important role in creating an image. Bright light can create the impression of openness and goodwill, while shadows can create an image of essence and intellectual potential. The correct use of lighting helps to emphasize the advantages of a politician's appearance and hide its shortcomings.

Shot composition is also an important tool. Placing a politician in the center of the frame emphasizes his importance, and using the rule of thirds creates a more harmonious and attractive image. The choice of background and scenery can also affect the perception of the politician's image. For example, an office-like background can emphasize his professionalism, while a natural landscape can emphasize his closeness to ordinary people. Thus, visual effects and editing serve as powerful tools for creating the desired image of a politician on television.

However, their misuse can have the opposite effect. One of the main discoveries in this field was the realization that editing can create intellectual and emotional tension by juxtaposing shots. This principle was widely used in silent and early sound films, where frames placed one after the other created new meaning that was not present in a single image. Further development of this theory showed that the combination of sound and visual images can enhance perception, create a special field for the viewer's imagination, and form unique images that are understandable on an emotional level.

Modern research and practice pay special attention to the rhythmic organization of frames and the auditory part, which helps to enhance the impact on the viewer. It should also be noted that editing includes not only visual techniques, but also work with sound, which complements and enhances perception, creating a complete audio-visual environment².

Sound is no less important than visual effects in shaping the image of a politician on television. Music and sound effects can evoke certain emotions in the audience, enhance or weaken the impression of the visual sequence.

¹ Невская Татьяна Александровна (2022). СМИ КАК ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ ИНСТРУМЕНТ И КАНАЛ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ И ПРОДВИЖЕНИЯ ИМИДЖА ПОЛИТИЧЕСКИХ ПАРТИЙ. Социодинамика, (10), 10-19.

² Воронова Т.А., & Богатырёв В.В. (2019). Монтаж как средство художественной выразительности в телепроизводстве. Актуальные вопросы современной филологии и журналистики, (2 (33)), 112-116.

For example, dynamic music can create an atmosphere of energy and optimism, while a calm tone can create confidence and stability. The use of dramatic music can emphasize the importance of an event or the emotionality of a politician's statements. Sound effects can also enhance the visual or add drama at certain moments.

A politician's voice is also an important element of his image. The timbre of the voice, intonation, speed of speech - all this affects the perception of his image and the audience's trust.

A confident and calm voice can give the impression of competence and authority, while a nervous or hesitant voice can express doubts about his abilities. The voice accompanying a video with the participation of a politician also plays an important role in shaping public opinion. The choice of words, the intonation of the speaker and the general mood of the text affect the audience's perception of the politician. A well-chosen voice can emphasize the politician's strengths and hide his weaknesses. In general, the voice is an integral part of the politician's television image and can significantly affect his perception by the audience. Therefore, its creation should be carefully thought out and professionally executed.

It should be noted that the effective use of sound is often closely related to visual images.

For example, a moment of high emotional intensity in a politician's speech can be expressed both with dynamic editing and with appropriate background music or sound effects. A harmonious combination of sound and image can significantly enhance the impact on the viewer and create a more vivid and memorable image. On the contrary, dissonance between visual and auditory sequences can negate all efforts to create a positive image.

In modern conditions, the role of sound design in online images and videos distributed through social networks is increasing. Here it is important to take into account the characteristics of the platforms and the behavior of the audience. Brevity and dynamism are the main factors for success in the online space. Therefore, sound should be as effective as possible and aimed at quick perception of information. The use of bright sound accents, dynamic editing and music that helps to quickly memorize and attract attention is the key to success in the online space. At the same time, excessive use of sound effects should be avoided so as not to distract from the main message.

Digital video processing technologies offer a wide range of, but also potentially dangerous, opportunities for political content creators. Modern editing programs allow you to make subtle color corrections, improve image quality, and remove unnecessary details and defects. These tools allow you to emphasize the desired features of a politician's appearance and make his image more attractive to the viewer. However, such opportunities pose a risk of distorting reality and manipulating public opinion.³

Color correction can change the perception of a politician's emotions, and improving image quality can hide signs of fatigue or aging. Removing unnecessary details (for example, bad gestures or facial expressions) creates an idealized image that may not correspond to reality.

³ Индюков Е.. Новые методы видеомонтажа и их применение в современном кинопроизводстве, рекламе, мобильных медиа и телевидении // Актуальные исследования. 2024. №45 (227). Ч.І.С. 64-84. URL: <https://apni.ru/article/10461-novye-metody-videomontazha-i-ih-primenenie-v-sovremennom-kinoproizvodstve-reklame-mobilnyh-media-i-televidenii>

In addition, modern programs allow for more complex manipulations, such as changing the politician's facial expressions and gestures using special effects. This allows you to create a completely artificial image that has nothing to do with reality. Adding or removing details from a video can change the context of events and confuse viewers.

In conclusion, digital video processing technology is a powerful tool that can be used to improve the quality of television content and manipulate public opinion. Therefore, it is necessary to critically evaluate the information presented on television and consider the possibilities of using technology to create a distorted image of a politician. It is necessary to develop mechanisms to monitor and verify the authenticity of video materials in a political context.